

AI and writing: Challenges and opportunities for ESP and professional communication

Marina BONDI, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy

Artificial intelligence (AI) has recently expanded its applications to almost all areas of human activity. Its ability to identify and predict language patterns has transformed academic and professional writing by empowering the creation, editing, and translation of texts. The article looks at the impact of AI in the context of specialized writing studies. After a brief overview of the literature on AI as a professional and learning tool, the article focuses on AI use in the various phases of (teaching) writing. The results of a small survey on the attitude of a group of students towards AI are presented in section 4, exploring both challenges and opportunities of using GPTs as resources for the teaching and learning of writing. Creativity and accuracy are seen as key issues. The paper closes with brief conclusions on the role of AI in specialized writing.

Keywords: Creativity; ESP; GPTs; LLMs; Professional Communication; Writing

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has recently expanded its applications to almost all areas of human activity. Its close link with information and language, however, has long been central to the development of AI and its impact on writing (Baron, 2023). Language manipulation has been a focus of interest since the beginning of computer science with Turing's work in the 30s, but the expression "artificial intelligence" dates back to 1955, when a group of scholars defined the field of AI as starting from an interest in "how to make machines use language, form abstractions and concepts, solve kinds of problems now reserved for humans, and improve themselves." (McCarthy et al., 2006, pp. 12-13). The development of AI has soon involved attention to specialized knowledge. The problem of encoding cultural knowledge, for example, has been an essential driver in the development of "expert systems" (Collins, 2012, p. 341), i.e., systems emulating human decision-making ability by combining an inference engine (applying inference rules) with a knowledge base that allowed the machine to elaborate new information.

Language translation and generation have been pivotal in AI progress. The history of machine translation shows the important move from the early rule-based models to later statistical models and machine learning as key elements

in determining success (Bowker & Buitrago, 2019). Based on multiple levels of neural networks, deep learning has recently resulted in significant improvements in the long history of attempts to produce efficient machine translation systems—see Yang et al. (2020) for a recent literature review. The steppingstones have been ‘Transformers’, deep learning architectures that rely on a parallel multi-head attention mechanism. Transformers require less training time than previous computing systems and have been adopted for training large language models (LLMs) on large (language) datasets. “Attention is all you need” (Vaswani et al., 2017, p. 2) vividly sums up the specificity of “a model architecture eschewing recurrence and instead relying entirely on an attention mechanism to draw global dependencies between input and output. The Transformer allows for significantly more parallelization and can reach a new state of the art in translation quality” (Vaswani et al., 2017, P. 2). Translation tasks have rapidly shown that transformers could achieve a new state of the art. A further development at Google AI has been BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers). BERT uses “masked language model” pre-training, which randomly masks some of the tokens from the input to predict the original vocabulary id of the masked word based only on its context and combines it with “next sentence prediction” (Devlin et al., 2018, pp. 1-2).

The impact of AI on writing itself is an even more recent phenomenon. Its ability to identify and predict language patterns has transformed professional writing by empowering the creation, editing, and translation of texts. AI tools can assist, augment, and even automate aspects of professional writing. Applications range from spell checkers and grammar correction tools to more sophisticated solutions for content generation and style improvement. The rapid development of AI technologies (Zhang et al., 2023) and their integration into the writing process have given rise to the need to study their impact, as well as the ethical and educational implications for the future of academic and professional writing.

The combination of publicly available ‘Generative Pre-Trained Transformers’ (GPTs) with the increasing volume of data available for their training has certainly influenced communication and learning. The advent of Open AI GPTs, exemplified by ChatGPT’s release in November 2022, has led to ChatGPT hype: the user base reached one hundred million people within two months. This also meant a rapid spread across colleges, with the consequent generalized concern about unethical use on the part of students in academic writing. The phenomenon rapidly led to the development of software that is intended to identify features of AI writing in written production, such as GPTZero.

The use of GPTs has also had a great impact in workplaces, where AI is used to write codes, carry out searches, and improve time management. As noted by

Liu et al. (2023), there has been significant interest in ChatGPT-related research, especially in the field of NLP (natural language processing) applications, but also in many other fields such as education, history, mathematics, medicine, and physics. The applications involved are numerous, in cyber security, customer support, health care, software development, consulting, etc. (Kalla & Smith, 2023). In all fields, it is important to assess the potential contribution of AI and at the same time balance it with its limits and potential risks.

The aim of this article is to look at the impact of AI in the context of specialized writing studies. After a brief overview of the literature on AI as a professional and learning tool (in the next section), the article focuses on AI use in the various phases of (teaching) writing (section 3). The results of a small survey on the attitude of a group of students towards AI are presented in section 4, exploring both challenges and opportunities. The paper will then close with brief conclusions on AI and specialized writing.

2. Background

The rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has not only changed the landscape of professional writing but also raised questions that warrant in-depth exploration and analysis. As already seen in the introduction, there are innumerable applications of AI, spanning information, language, robots, creative works, gaming, law, and so on. Two key areas are in focus here: professional discourse and academic contexts.

2.1. AI in professional discourse

AI has changed professional communication and job prospects in many fields, such as professional mentorship (Bagai & Mane, 2023), science communication (Schäfer, 2023), journalism and sports (Türksoy, 2022), or law (e.g., legal research and legal analytics). It has radically transformed the process of translation, where the role of human agents is slowly changing from translator to post-editor (Jakobsen, 2019).

The field of science has long been invested directly, both in terms of science communication and in professional practice. The medical field, to take just one example, pays increasing attention to challenges, opportunities and future directions of AI and machine learning in medicine, from clinical applications to imaging interpretation and infectious-diseases surveillance (cf. Beam et al., 2023), as well as to the advanced medical reasoning abilities of recent applications (Moor et al., 2023).

Business communication is also a key area in which AI has been shown to have a profound influence (Brown-Devlin et al., 2022; Cardon et al., 2023; Getchell et al., 2022; Men et al., 2022). There is a wide range of tools available for the

market. Tools for team communication and meetings (often integrated into collaboration platforms) are just the most obvious examples. The field of augmented writing and text summarization tools is rapidly expanding: there are programmes like Grammarly for writing assistance, Textio for job position announcements, or GPTs to generate emails, reports or specific documents. Employers also avail themselves of communication evaluation and training tools, providing sentiment analysis or offering tailored and individualized feedback and assessments, like HireVue for job interviews. Conversational agents are also used to develop ideas with the help of assistants such as Project Debater and in general tools for argument mining (Getchell et al., 2022).

AI applications extend across marketing, sales, customer service, legal analysis and HR (human resources), with projections of major job losses and displacement (Lowrey, 2023). AI-assisted writing is expanding and is bound to have an impact on professional communication (Cardon et al., 2023). Using AI as a resource may represent a key opportunity for more efficient revision and brainstorming, but of course there are concerns about accountability, agency, and authenticity, and the general perception is that AI literacy will represent a key challenge in the future. The fear is that handing writing over to AI might have a negative impact on human critical thinking and creativity (Baron, 2023).

The accuracy of GPTs is also understandably quite a central issue in NLP studies and users' perceptions. By July 2023, it was noted that users began to complain about the accuracy of ChatGPT and experimental work showed that for example the performance and behaviour of GPT 3.5 and GPT 4 can vary greatly over time (Chen et al., 2023). At the same time, it was observed that the average time spent on ChatGPT started to decrease, with a small increase in unique visitors. However, despite fluctuations, ChatGPT continues to attract over one hundred million monthly active users (Shewale, 2023).

2.2. AI in higher education

In academia, AI presents complex challenges, especially concerning, first of all, academic integrity (Cotton et al., 2023; Purwanto & Nurhamidah, 2021; Rudolph et al., 2023; Swiecki et al., 2022; Yu, 2023). GPTs pose authorship problems: since chatbots are not human, there is no copyright protection on their work and, at the same time, their work can hardly be considered authorial work (even if many think their use should be declared). The most immediate challenge for educators has been that students can hand in assignments produced by ChatGPT without mentioning the source, thus gaining credit for content that they themselves are not able to create, a form of academic malpractice that is an analogue to plagiarism. As a result, many have felt AI represents a serious threat to the college essay (e.g., Marche, 2022) and universities (as well as journals) have struggled with the need to establish policies on the use of AI. Educators have also felt the need to explore student's

attitudes to AI-related plagiarism—*AI-giarism*—as an emergent form of academic dishonesty (Chan, 2024). From a wider perspective, and perhaps more alarmingly, the introduction of AI into writing can also be seen as a threat to writing skills and the central role writing has long played in the development of ideas (Baron, 2023). The risk is one of “deskilling,” i.e., reducing the level of skill required to carry out writing.

The introduction of AI in writing has rapidly given rise to several problematic questions. Accessibility and equity represent a problem that is deeply felt in academia: access to data is unequal and influenced by individual abilities and economic conditions, as well as the degree of digital literacy. Bias is another major area of concern: as LLMs work on available data, there are concerns about potential discriminatory outcomes for minority backgrounds, or simply non-English-speaking populations and non-western cultures. Finally, questions of accuracy have been a focal point: data quality can be affected by imbalance, lack of generalizability, ambiguous data, but also changes in the data or insufficient data on specific specialized areas. Ultimately, it is important to remember that LLMs can ‘hallucinate’, i.e., generate plausible content that is not factual at all, in ways that give rise to serious concern over their reliability. The feature that has attracted the most attention in GPTs is their dialogic dimension. Conversational AI is rooted in interactive question-and-answer patterns, highlighting the fact that the machine is responsive to follow-up: it can learn from the feedback humans provide and thus finetune the output. This points to the key role of effective prompting and ‘prompt engineering’. Effective prompting is important from the point of view of both programming (Denny et al., 2023) and developing students’ language awareness (Dynel, 2023). It is essential to choose words carefully when asking a GPT to take up a writing task; purpose and focus must be defined in concise and specific terms, providing context and stimulating revision to “keep the conversation on track” (Atlas, 2023, pp. 43-44). Strategically, it may be useful to act as a persona or to indicate a specific perspective, providing prompts in layers through a ‘matrix’ approach to the topic. When considered from this point of view, GPTs not only provide new tools for the development of writing but also pose new challenges to learners and professionals. The need to develop prompting skills is debated widely on the web, in social media (cf. the subreddit on Prompt Design and blogs, with a proliferation of sites suggesting prompting, especially in content creation.¹ Practical introductions to the use of GPTs in higher education usually involve explicit attention to different kinds of prompts; Atlas (2023), for example, has a full chapter of “effective prompts” (p. 41) but also illustrates every chapter with specific prompts for activities in supporting writing, communication, and individualized learning.

The attention paid by academics to the impact of AI on their activities is reflected in research on English for Specific Purposes (ESP). Perspectives vary,

focusing on teaching methodology (Kovačević, 2023), curriculum design (Tang, 2023) and testing (Ningsih, 2023; Martinez- Comesaña, 2023; Moqbel et al., 2023). AI may help teachers in developing materials for academic and technical writing skills. It can help with the production of vocabulary and grammar exercises or in providing instant feedback in the form of individualized learning. Collaboration between ESP scholars and computer scientists has fine-tuned AI tools, especially in areas like automatic writing evaluation (Putri Ramahandty et al., 2023) and in the conversational interface of chatbots, with their potential as generative virtual tutors (Ahmed et al., 2023; Atlas, 2023) used in interactive learning as sources of questions and recommendations.

When focusing on writing, it soon becomes evident that the machine easily moves from tool to partner (Burkhard et al., 2022). Human-machine teaming can lead to different collaborative roles, ranging from mere resources (as with grammar and spelling checkers) to assistants in research and copy-editing functions (e.g., Google Smart Compose) and even partners in writing, thus automatically giving rise to questions of authorship (McKee & Porter, 2022). What human beings need to add to the collaboration with an AI partner is their rhetorical intelligence: they should be able to analyze the audience and identify what is needed in a particular situation, choose arguments by ethics and practical wisdom, and ultimately produce value for the audience (McKee & Porter, 2022).

From the point of view of language learning, finally, the focus is on what can be learnt by interacting with AI. Learners can develop their skills both by studying the output of GPTs and by prompting the transformer. Using the output of GPTs, they can focus on organizational patterns of plausible text, they can observe patterns and study transformations in genre conventions, style and tone as well as assess output and identify errors. What has attracted the most attention, however, is prompting. This is a key learning activity requiring fine metalinguistic awareness: interacting with AI may raise metalinguistic, metadiscursive, metacommunicative, and metapragmatic awareness (Dyrel, 2023). Learners may learn to adjust output to different prompts, offering examples, developing a chain of thought, and ultimately learning to draft effective prompts.

In a more general perspective, the role of AI in writing represents both a challenge and an opportunity. AI can be seen as a writing tool that helps students and professionals to plan, write, and revise their work. On the other hand, even leaving aside issues of cheating and plagiarism, the risk is that AI may weaken their planning and revising skills, if not their personal writing voice: learning to see AI output as a suggestion that can be accepted or rejected becomes critical.

The pervasiveness of AI makes it essential to develop digital literacy in both educational and professional contexts (Cardon et al., 2023; Getchell et al., 2022; Vance et al., 2023). Digital literacy includes different skills. The first is probably understanding the tools and aligning them appropriately with the task. But equally important is to keep in mind questions of authenticity, thus focusing on genuine communication and adding the human element to what is provided by the system. In general, it is also crucial to control the agency of the process, retain decision-making rights, and keep accountability in mind, ascertaining the reliability of the content and ensuring equity and fairness.

In conclusion, AI's integration into professional and ESP writing presents a dynamic landscape filled with possibilities, challenges and evolving considerations. Language and communication teachers need to keep a balance between embracing the advantages and addressing ethical and authenticity concerns. With a tertiary-level teaching/learning perspective in view, the next section analyses AI-supported writing in the different phases of the writing process.

3. Supporting ESP/professional writing with AI

What can generative pre-trained transformers do for ESP/professional writing? They can offer users a wide range of resources: they can provide access to information, search for relevant literature and materials, summarize content, produce questions, and generate points for an outline. However, there are significant problems with accuracy and users should be encouraged to evaluate answers, rather than accept them unthinkingly. As stated by the chatbot, 'ChatGPT may produce inaccurate information about people, places, or facts'. Both teachers and learners need to be aware of the limitations of GPTs in terms of accuracy, to be able to choose how to use them.

The following subsections provide an outline of activities carried out with prompts on ChatGPT in the various stages of writing to explore its potential use. The two basic functions of transformers for ESP or professional writers are content generation and style improvement. These are usually variously balanced in the different stages of the writing process: while content generation dominates the pre-writing phase, style improvement is key in the revision (post-writing) phase, and the two are interwoven in the while-writing phase and in activities that develop the skills that are necessary for the core of the writing process.

3.1. Pre-writing

Before writing it is always useful to carry out a literature review to map the field and see what has been written: it is important to establish what information is available and—in the case of argumentative writing—what

positions have been taken (or what position should be taken). AI can be useful in identifying sources and in developing ideas that can be useful in preparing different kinds of tasks.

ChatGPT can be asked to provide sources, when these are available on the internet; scientific references, however, may turn out to be limited and inaccurate. In one instance ChatGPT was asked to provide a bibliography on AI and ESP. The result was a list of seven references which were then double-checked manually on databases, with the result that two were totally irrelevant and two could not be found through abstracting services. Chat GPT was then asked to summarize these two papers. The result was that it admitted that one of the papers listed did not exist (1) and the other was not in the database it could access (2).

- (1) I apologize for the confusion, but the paper titled “The Impact of Effective Communication in Professional Settings” by Smith, Johnson, and Williams (2019) is not a real paper, and I cannot provide a summary of its content since it does not exist in my knowledge base. If you have a different paper or topic you'd like me to summarize or discuss, please provide the necessary details, and I'd be happy to assist you.
- (2) I apologize, but I do not have access to the specific content of individual research papers or conference proceedings, and I cannot provide a summary of the paper titled “AI in Professional Writing: Impacts, opportunities, and challenges” by E. H. Hovy, as it is not in my database. If you have specific questions or need information on a related topic, please feel free to ask, and I'll do my best to provide relevant information based on my training data up to September, 2021.

Responses can be vague, inaccurate, or wrong. Optimization strategies in prompting might have led to better results, by asking for example to list only references that could be accessed and by asking ChatGPT to provide a summary of the papers. However, there is no way of overcoming the limits of the training data (September, 2021 for GPT 3.5, as of October, 2023). Users need to weigh the effort of refining prompts and checking the output of the GPT, as individual web searches may be much more efficient than AI-supported searches.

An interesting contribution that ChatGPT can provide to the pre-writing phase is generating ideas. Brainstorming allows people to develop ideas and understanding of a topic. AI is often used in training medical personnel to observe potential issues, but its value for pre-writing activities is not fully recognized in teaching practices. Critical thinking can be characterized in terms of: “understanding and analyzing ideas and arguments,” “evaluating

ideas and arguments,” and “solving problems and making decisions.”² The first two skills are quite central in preparation for writing and can become the focus of pre-writing activities. GPTs can be used to generate potential topics or arguments, to question and evaluate beliefs, to examine and interpret ideas, as well as to clarify issues. Asking ChatGPT to generate a list of possible subtopics or arguments may be a good starting point for individual reflection or group discussion. In argumentative writing, learners could ask the chatbot for arguments and counterarguments on an issue (e.g., a prompt could be “list 10 reasons for/against . . .”). Writers can then use this list to define their own positions, after checking for unintentional bias. With more informational tasks, learners could ask ChatGPT to list the aspects to be considered, or they could list the information easily available and ask the chatbot to check what other information might be required or useful. It is always important to assess the ideas offered by the GPT, as the information on which they are based can be false. Other prewriting activities for learners could be the following. Students can ask the GPT to produce an argumentative piece of writing and reflect on whether they agree or not. If not, they can be asked to refute the arguments. In a task-based perspective, students and teachers can ask a GPT for writing stimuli: e.g., a vacancy notice for which they can write an application. Learners write an outline for the application and ask the chatbot to assess their outline and provide suggestions for further information to be added.

3.2. While writing

AI-supported writing activities are based primarily on the skills of GPTs as text generators, as they can analyze regularities in their training data and complete or generate text from given prompts. The most productive contribution of chatbots seems to be their awareness of regularities. Their ability to identify patterns can be exploited at different levels, ranging from lexico-grammatical activities to tasks on textual organization and style.

The completion of sentences is obviously based on lexico-grammatical competence and can support writing with suggestions. Completion will be based on and reflect training data. In general, ChatGPT has been instructed to avoid the most obvious biases and when asked to complete sentences like “Women are usually . . . Men are usually . . .,” the chatbot will not be caught by bias: it will show awareness of ethical guidelines but still produce generalizations that reflect a widely shared trend:

- (3) It's important to avoid making sweeping generalizations about gender, as individuals can vary widely. However, if you'd like to discuss general societal expectations or stereotypes, you could say that women are usually associated with nurturing roles, while men are usually

associated with leadership roles. Please keep in mind that these are stereotypes and do not apply to every individual.

ChatGPT is also capable of completing texts, but it is important to provide all the information that we want to be present in the text; otherwise, the chatbot will produce spontaneous text based on the interpretation of the text type required and on the experience of examples encountered. When asked to complete a text beginning with 'The man entered the room', for example, the response is an elaborate description of the room full of unsolicited data, unless the information was provided directly. The chatbot can produce long texts, and texts that are tuned to the prompted genres, but appropriate guidance is necessary. In order to avoid generating the wrong kind of text, it is necessary to provide all the information to be included and clear indications of the purpose of the text, the length, the reader, and the style to be adopted. Accurate prompting should restrict options to prevent the GPT from providing the templates that are most widely used in the training data. When using ChatGPT to write a CV, for example, it is important to provide all the information about the individual; otherwise, it will simply generate a plausible but generic CV.

Chatbots are designed to elaborate a notion. When asked to elaborate on a basic definition of corporate vision (e.g., "A business vision is your goal for what your business will be in the future."), they can follow the style adopted in the first sentence and elaborate on that:

- (4) A business vision is your goal for what your business will be in the future. It serves as a guiding light, outlining your company's long-term aspirations, values, and the impact you hope to make on your industry or the world. This vision statement provides direction, motivates your team, and helps you make strategic decisions to realize your desired future. It's a source of inspiration that goes beyond short-term objectives, painting a vivid picture of where you aim to take your business and what you want it to represent.

Before adopting the text provided, however, it is necessary to assess whether it is appropriate to the specific context, the reader addressed and the specific voice required. The analytical skills of chatbots also make them very good at adapting texts to a specified style, as well as refining and reducing texts. Given the text in 4, for example, ChatGPT was asked to rewrite it in a more formal, academic style. The version produced by the chatbot features longer sentences, no personal references and more formal lexical choices:

- (5) A business vision encapsulates the future-oriented aspirations and values of an enterprise, delineating its long-term trajectory, intended

impact on its industry or broader societal context, and foundational principles. Functioning as a guiding beacon, this vision statement serves to provide strategic direction, fostering motivation within the organizational team, and facilitating informed decision-making processes. In essence, the business vision transcends transient objectives, offering a source of enduring inspiration by articulating a comprehensive and vivid portrayal of the envisioned future state of the enterprise and the values it aspires to embody.

Reformulation can be accurate and typically reflects the elements focused on in the prompt (whether meta-linguistic, metapragmatic, meta-discursive or meta-communicative). Responses may vary, but they will still be based on the same text type/genre framework. Of course, the accuracy and appropriateness of the content chosen should be subject to critical scrutiny by the writer.

Teachers can use this type of exercise to help students focus on both the generic structure and authorial voice of their texts, thus exploring the key tension between commonality and individuality that characterizes all specialized discourse. The text produced by the chatbot should be taken as a mere example of a plausible text, to be adapted to the specific situation in which we are writing. Users can rely on AI to be good at identifying the generic structures and stylistic features of texts, but they should be guided to assess the output of the chatbot and to decide how to use it to fit their writing objectives.

3.3. Post-writing

Finally, GPTs can be used for revision. This is an essential step for first-language (L1) and second-language (L2) writing alike, but focusing on accuracy and fluency is particularly relevant for L2 learners.

ChatGPT can be given prompts to check spelling, punctuation, collocation, and grammar. It can be asked to improve clarity, concision, and flow. It can suggest rephrasing, produce summaries of long sections, and provide comments, feedback, corrections, and explanations of mistakes. Here is an example of the prompt (6) and the suggestions provided by ChatGPT (7):

- (6) Prompt: Can you revise the following text, from an email, providing feedback and explanations for mistakes? Here is the text: • I am convinced that we have all worked very hard to get shipping instructions and everything else sorted out on time. Therefore, I believe there is nothing we should blame us that we did not focus doing during December. However, what I would like every one of us to reflect on is

our somewhat poor or at least partial understanding of the Markets and their needs.

- (7) ChatGPT: Certainly! Here's a revised version of the text with feedback and explanations for the changes:

"I am convinced that we have all worked very hard to get shipping instructions and everything else sorted out on time. Therefore, I believe there is nothing we should blame ourselves for not focusing on during December. However, what I would like each one of us to reflect on is our somewhat poor, or at least partial, understanding of the markets and their needs."

Feedback and Explanations:

- *Pronoun Agreement:*

Original: "... nothing we should blame us ..."

Revised: "... nothing we should blame ourselves for ..."

Explanation: Corrected the pronoun agreement. "Blame ourselves" is the correct form, indicating that the blame should be placed on the individuals involved.

- *Redundancy and Clarity:*

Original: "... nothing we should blame ourselves that we did not focus doing during December."

Revised: "... nothing we should blame ourselves for not focusing on during December."

Explanation: Clarified the sentence by removing redundancy and improving readability. "For not focusing on" is a more concise and clear expression.

- *Consistency and Parallel Structure:*

Original: "... every one of us ..."

Revised: "... each one of us ..."

Explanation: Maintained consistency by using "each one of us" instead of "everyone of us" for better parallel structure.

- *Punctuation:*

Original: "... poor or at least partial understanding of the Markets ..."

Revised: "... poor, or at least partial, understanding of the markets ..."

Explanation: Added commas after "poor" and "partial" to improve punctuation and make the sentence clearer.

Overall, the revisions aim to enhance clarity, correct grammatical errors, and improve the overall structure of the text.

When using these tools in class, however, it is always important to guide learners to pay attention to potential errors made by ChatGPT, as this may misunderstand their meanings or complete with the wrong assumptions. A further round of peer review may be useful anyway. Other post-writing activities where GPTs can be useful involve comparing texts. One could ask the GPT to write a similar text and then carry out a comparison in terms of structure and style with students.

Overall, two main issues should be kept in mind when relying on AI as a support for writing. The first is to check the accuracy of the information, as AI-generated texts are only plausible, not necessarily accurate. Even more importantly, we should adapt the text produced to the voice that represents the speaker: is this the way we want to sound? Is this our discursive identity? Is this really what we want to say? Altogether then, once more, the solutions suggested should be adapted rather than adopted.

4. Millennials and AI: Challenges and opportunities

The number of studies reflecting on the need to integrate forms of AI literacy in academic or professional writing is growing systematically, often leading to new acronyms, such as AIAP-Artificial Intelligence for Academic Purposes (Ngo & Hastie, 2025). The field is evolving quickly and practical guidance on how to integrate AI tools in the teaching/learning of writing is still largely needed.

The sequence of points dealt with in section 3 above was the object of a hands-on session on the use of ChatGPT with a group of MA students attending a course in 'Professional communication and digital discourse' in the autumn of, 2023. The students received a brief introduction to the present role of AI, with preliminary definitions and notes on its potential and limits. Then the students went through several activities meant to introduce the main features of texts produced by GPTs, to raise students' awareness of ethical and accuracy problems, as well as to focus on the role of GPTs as resources in the different phases of writing (pre-writing, while writing and post-writing), with activities that paid attention to the key features of effective prompting.

Before the hands-on session, the students were asked to respond to a preparatory questionnaire on the use of AI in writing. The questionnaire was the one used by Professor Naomi Baron in 2022 (before the release of ChatGPT) both with US students and Italian ones (Baron, 2023, Chapter 12). Of the 80 students registered for the course, only 56 responded to the questionnaire. The sample is certainly not representative of much else than Italian classes in languages for international communication, but it was a good preparation for a hands-on workshop and for a focus group to follow. The focus of the questionnaire was on writing in general and the use of AI. The following is an overview of the responses regarding AI for writing.

Figure 1a/b/c.
Questionnaire Results

When responding to the question “If you had an AI program that could write a short essay for you, would you use it?” about half of the students responded ‘No’, while the other half admitted that they would try it, even if just for fun. With the question “If an AI program writes a poem or short story, do you think the result should be called creative?” most students responded ‘No’. The results are in line with Baron’s results, in which 40% of students replied that they would try AI just for fun. The results reflect a slight increase in curiosity after the ChatGPT hype and a persistent skepticism about the relationship between AI and creativity, seen as an irreplaceable characteristic of human beings.

Similarly, when asked to indicate which professions they felt to be more at risk, most students mentioned translators, while lawyers, journalists, playwrights, and poets were perceived as less at risk. Some additional comments left by the

students considered AI as a threat to their jobs, but also emphasized the importance of human creativity:

- (1) I think AI should be used as a tool to help us, but it should not substitute human beings. It's something that can help us get better results, but it lacks the human component.
- (2) AI is going to cover a large part of today's job situation, so humans have to be creative and create new job placements that can't be covered by AI).

Another set of questions addressed the role of GPTs in different kinds of writing:

- What is one kind of writing you would be happy to hand over to ChatGPT?
- What is one kind of writing on which you would like to collaborate with ChatGPT?
- What is one kind of writing you would like to retain to do by yourself, not asking for help from ChatGPT?

Figure 2.

Writing Tasks that can be Handed over to ChatGPT

When responding to the first question, 58% of students replied that they would be happy to hand over to ChatGPT formal writing, such as academic work, emails, and job applications. Only 10 % stated that they would have been happy to hand over creative work, while the remaining respondents would either delegate other forms of writing (e.g., personal fitness gym programmes) or nothing at all.

Figure 3.
Collaborating with ChatGPT

When asked to specify a kind of writing on which they would have liked to collaborate with ChatGPT, 52% of students mentioned academic work, while 17% professional writing (e.g., emails, letters . . .) and job applications. The remaining ones admitted that they would use ChatGPT for creative works and social media.

Figure 4.
Writing not to be Left to ChatGPT

When asked to indicate one kind of writing that they would have liked to retain to do by themselves, not asking for help from ChatGPT, most respondents mentioned creative work and more complex forms of academic writing (e.g., dissertations), which are presumably perceived to require personal elements that AI lacks:

- (3) I think this AI tool can be useful in writing standard emails, something that has a fix (sic) structure. However, I think it lacks the personal details and information you may need for a diary or a personal email/letter.
- (4) Actually, I would rely on my personal competences in writing, even if I'm not so good at it, rather than using chatGPT. I think it may be useful for that kind of writing related to the academic field, like essay because they have a typical structure and therefore it may be useful to understand the way they need to be made.

Overall, the results show varied degrees of openness towards ChatGPT and considerable attention paid to the importance of creativity.

After the hands-on session, the students discussed in small focus groups how the activities had influenced their perceptions of AI. The workshop on ChatGPT that followed the questionnaire was aimed at discussing ChatGPT as a writing and learning resource. The notes taken during the discussion and the final reports highlighted greater openness to experimenting with AI for professional writing (email, cover letter, presentations) but also much greater awareness of limitations. Students emphasized that they had realized how ChatGPT could be a tool for writing by providing starting points, but they had also become more aware of its limits as an information source. While confirming that they had no interest in leaving their personal communication to AI, they also said they had acquired greater awareness of ethical issues, including privacy and academic integrity.

5. Summing up challenges and opportunities

The public launch of ChatGPT has stimulated an intense public debate on some key issues in AI-supported writing, such as possible bias (Caliskan, 2023; Ray, 2023), different levels of accuracy and reliability (Amaro et al., 2023; Reiss, 2023; Shen et al., 2023), data privacy (Gupta et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2023), and the need for different types of digital literacy, such as information, data and privacy literacy (Lund et al., 2023), including the ethical dimension.

The undeniable efficiency of GPTs presents risks and opportunities at the same time. In education and professional training, the use of generative AI should go hand in hand with the development of specific literacies in matters of authenticity, agency, accountability and equity. The key opportunities most scholars see in the development of AI for writing lie in the use of AI as a writing resource. Provided the decision-making process remains in the hands of human users, AI can be used for data processing and retrieval, for critical thinking practice in better idea generation, as well as for supporting revision and providing feedback on grammar and style. The key risks, however, are

directly related to the opportunities: they are the risk of passive use on the part of learners, which could in turn lead to a negative impact on critical thinking and authenticity, and the risk of handing over to AI some of the responsibilities of teachers as active agents through personal interaction with their learners.

The acknowledged potential use of AI in specialized and professional writing offers (or maybe imposes) a new research agenda for writing studies. Many research areas emerge as relevant. First of all, mention should be made of the study of how perceptions of AI are likely to change (e.g., Baron, 2023; Cardon et al., 2023). How will issues of trust and bias develop as technology develops and policies are implemented? How will the demographics change in terms of age and position of AI users? A second area of investigation could be the study of the new writing practices. How do users of generative AI change their writing habits? What do they write with or without AI? How does their use of AI vary in intercultural contexts, in L1 or L2? A third important focus would be on how writing itself—as an output—might change. Does AI-supported writing have an impact on textual organization or lexico-grammar?

A further interesting area could focus on how specific forms of tool design affect writing. Is the final output affected by the affordances, by the “human” qualities of the chatbot, and by the opportunities for collaboration? The audience could be another factor. How do different audiences influence the nature of the product? Last, but not least, perhaps even most importantly from a teaching/learning perspective, it is important to examine the impact of AI on the development of language skills and language awareness at different levels of education. What kind of digital literacy is required for the technology to contribute to the development of language learning and language awareness, beyond the mere “lure of efficiency” (Baron, 2023)? Many questions lie ahead, making the issue a very interesting one for literacy studies.

Notes

1. See for example: <https://chatgptaihub.com/chatgpt-prompts-for-content-creation/>; <https://socialbee.com/blog/ai-social-media-prompts/>; <https://sticai.com/prompts>
2. See Cambridge Life Competencies framework. The other areas included are: Creative Thinking, learning to Learn, Communication, Collaboration, and Social Responsibilities. (<https://www.cambridge.org/gb/cambridge-english/better-learning-insights/cambridgelifecompetenciesframework>)

The Author

Marina Bondi (Email: marina.bondi@unimore.it) is Professor of English Linguistics at the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia. Founding Director

of the *CLAVIER* centre (*Corpus and Language Variation in English Research*), she has published extensively in the field of genre analysis, EAP and corpus linguistics, with a focus on language variation across genres, disciplines and cultures. Her publications have appeared in international journals such as *Pragmatics*, *IJBC*, *Journal of Pragmatics*, *Written Communication*, *IEEE Transactions in Professional Communication*, *Discourse Context & Media*, *Lingua* etc. She is Associate-Editor of *ESP journal*. Her recent interest centres on knowledge dissemination and the impact of digital media on specialized discourse.

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